

Supplementary Material – M-estimation

M-estimate function in robust statistics downweight the contribution of errors with large amplitudes. However, there are in general two major classes of M-estimate function, namely monotonic or redescending functions. Monotonic function includes the conventional square function (which is not robust but it can achieve high efficiency, i.e. better accuracy for Gaussian errors), the absolute function (which is commonly used in L1-based robust estimation), and the Huber function (a square function and a linear function respectively for error magnitude smaller or larger than a given threshold), etc. Redescending M-estimate function, which resembles an amplitude clipper, will level off larger error magnitude so that outliers with large magnitudes are suppressed. Commonly used redescending M-estimate functions include the Hampel's redescending function and the Turkey biweight or bisquare functions.

The performance measures of robustness of estimators include (c.f. Sections 3.1 to 3.3 [9]) influence function (IF), breakdown point (BP) and asymptotic bias.

Theoretically, redescending M-estimators are more robust than monotone M-estimators because they are not sensitivity to the amplitude of the outliers, which is sometimes measured in terms of the concept of influence function (IF) and sensitivity curves (SC). The sensitivity of monotone estimators can go to infinity if the amplitude of the observation outlier goes to infinity. This is not the case for redescending M-estimators as large amplitude errors will be completely ignored. For both explanation and response variables outliers, redescending M-estimator will only be large when the error or residual magnitude falls below the threshold. Therefore, a robust scale estimator to determine these threshold related parameters is very important. This is not the case for monotone estimators (c.f. Section 5.4.2 [9]).

The finite break point (FBP) on the other hand measures the fraction of observations that can be corrupted before the estimator becomes unbound and hence its maximum value is 0.5, because if more than half of the observations are corrupted, then the original observations would not be treated as inliers but rather as outliers. The break point for redescending estimator is $\varepsilon = \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{n - k^* - 1}{2} \right)$ where k^* is some quantities less than P the order of the explanatory variable vector and n is the number of observations. [eqn. (5.10) in [24]. For large n , one can see that ε tends to the desired value of 0.5. For monotone estimators, the FBP can be 0 because a "large x_i " in the explanatory variable vector \mathbf{x} will dominate the fit as the error measure is not bounded.

As large outliers in monotone M-estimators are only suppressed but not completely removed in redescending M-estimators, it will result in a larger bias over the latter. While the maximum asymptotic bias of the Huber estimator is small, the average overall bias due to the entire range of large outliers above the threshold is substantially larger than good redescending M-estimators such as the MM-estimators.

While redescending M-estimator has outstanding robustness, its efficiency for Gaussian distributed errors can be low, say the S-estimator can only achieve a typical 28.7% efficiency over the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE), which in turns is much better than the least median squares and the least trimmed squares methods. The MM estimator is well known for its ability to achieve a high FBP and a selected efficiency simultaneously, say 85% efficiency at normal. It relies on a robust S-estimator to provide a robust initial scale estimate and a novel iterative process to achieve a given efficiency with theoretical guarantee [RS1]. In particular, any solution to the M-estimation equation has the same efficiency as the global minimum. The S-estimator however also requires a good initial guess via randomization etc, which can be computational very expensive.

In our case, we use the MAD to estimate the scale parameter. In principle, the S-estimator is more robust than the median for scale estimation. However, its high complexity is not too suitable for online applications. Here, we explore the sequential nature of the iteration to recursive update the scale parameters and detect possible corrupted observations, which leads to better efficiency at a significantly lower complexity. Since the regression involves in the AR estimation has its input and observations derived from the input time series, cleaning of possible corrupted observations can significantly mitigate their adverse effect. As practical applications seldom involve up to 50% of outliers, a MAD type of estimator with a suitably chosen window size has been shown to work well. Simulations have demonstrated the effectiveness of our proposed approach.

Finally, regarding the comparison between the Hampel's and other redescending estimators such as the Turkey bisquares or biweight function, it is our experience that their performances are kind of similar, though the bisweight function has a continuous derivative and hence it is theoretically preferred. The reason is due to the fact the asymptotic variance of the estimator is proportional to $\nu = E_F[\psi^2] / E_F[\psi']$, where \mathbf{F} is the data distribution. If \mathbf{F} has lot of

probability mass at the discontinuity of the M-estimate function, then the denominator may be substantially increased. However, this type of situation seldom occurs in practical and hence the practical performances of the two estimators are similar. The most important task is in fact the selection of the robust scale parameter, i.e. σ_E . Nevertheless, both the Hampel's and bisquares functions can be used in our framework and we preferred to use the Hampel's function due to its simplicity in implementation.

[9] R. A. Maronna, R. D. Martin, and V. J. Yohai, *Robust Statistics: Theory and Methods*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, March 2006.

[RS1] V. J. Yohai, "High breakdown-point and high efficiency estimates for regression," *The Annals of Statistics*, 15, pp. 642-656, 1987.

IMPACT OF DATA CLEANING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT METHODS 15% OUTLIER OCCURRENCE

Method	Parameter Estimation Error (Mean L_2 -Error)		Variable Selection Accuracy (%)	
	Without cleaning	With Cleaning	Without cleaning	With Cleaning
OLS	0.735	0.146	-*	-*
LASSO	0.165	0.144	20	25
ALASSO	0.093	0.083	62	84
LAD-LASSO	0.263		12	

IMPACT OF DATA CLEANING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT METHODS 10% OUTLIER OCCURRENCE

Method	Parameter Estimation Error (Mean L_2 -Error)		Variable Selection Accuracy (%)	
	Without cleaning	With Cleaning	Without cleaning	With Cleaning
OLS	0.681	0.133	-*	-*
LASSO	0.139	0.105	23	31
ALASSO	0.104	0.074	67	90
LAD-LASSO	0.242		15	

IMPACT OF DATA CLEANING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT METHODS 5% OUTLIER. (ALREADY SHOWED IN THE MAIN MANUSCRIPT)

Method	Parameter Estimation Error (Mean L_2 -Error)		Variable Selection Accuracy (%)	
	Without cleaning	With Cleaning	Without cleaning	With Cleaning
OLS	0.66	0.12	-*	-*
LASSO	0.27	0.11	22	31
ALASSO	0.31	0.07	60	91
LAD-LASSO	0.1547		24	